

Firm-Specific Attributes and Share Price Volatility of Listed Industrial Goods Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of firm specific attributes on share price volatility by obtaining empirical evidence from firms listed in the industrial goods sector in the Nigerian Exchange. Share price volatility was measured with reference to percentage changes in share prices for the study period (from 2014 to 2024) whereas, the specific attributes of firms analysed in this study were measures of financial leverage, profitability, and liquidity. Based on the *ex-post facto* research design, the study adopted the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) model to analyse the study's data. Results from the analytical process indicate that financial leverage exerts negative but statistically insignificant effect on share price volatility ($\beta = -0.170778$, $p = 0.5879$), suggesting that financial leverage does not have significant influence on share price volatility. Also, profitability evinced a positive but statistically insignificant association with share price volatility ($\beta = 0.449844$, $p = 0.4613$), indicating that more profitable firms may experience moderate fluctuations in their share prices. Similarly, liquidity exhibits an insignificant positive effect on share price volatility ($\beta = -0.006460$, $p = 0.7690$). Based on these findings, the recommendation is that firms' executives should adopt prudent financial policies, including maintaining optimal leverage levels, to bolster investor confidence and support market stability. Investors should closely monitor profitability indicators, as increases may signal impending share price volatility and associated risks or opportunities. Additionally, regulatory authorities are encouraged to develop reporting standards that emphasize the volatility implications of profitability to aid market participants' decision-making. This study contributes to the empirical literature by employing the GMM methodology, thus enriching the methodological diversity in volatility research within the Nigerian context.

Keywords: Firm Specific Attributes, Share Price Volatility, Listed Industrial Goods Firms

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The nexus between firm-specific attributes and share price behaviour has long occupied a central position in finance and investment research. Investors rely extensively on firm-level characteristics to assess asset value, forecast future performance, and make informed portfolio decisions (Oyedokun, & Yunusa, 2017; Rehman, Kai, & Xue, 2025). Firm attributes, broadly classified as financial or non-financial, encompass a wide range of indicators such as profitability, leverage, liquidity, firm age, earnings quality, and corporate governance (Habib et al., 2022; Bodie, Kane, & Marcus, 2014). These attributes provide essential information for market participants to evaluate risk and return profiles, thereby shaping firm valuation and price dynamics.

In emerging economies such as Nigeria, the capital market remains a critical channel for mobilizing savings and facilitating investment. However, the market is often characterized by low liquidity, limited investor participation, and high levels of sentiment-driven trading.

Consequently, understanding the role of firm-level fundamentals in explaining share price movements is vital for improving market efficiency and investor confidence. Despite the importance of these issues, empirical studies in Nigeria have largely emphasized macroeconomic and market-wide determinants of stock performance, with relatively limited attention to firm-specific factors; particularly within the industrial goods sector, a key driver of the nation's real economy.

Theoretically, leverage increases financial risk and may amplify share price volatility due to heightened exposure to financial distress (Udin, Khan, & Javid, 2017; Uwuigbe et al., 2015). Conversely, higher profitability is typically associated with operational stability and reduced volatility (Nenu, Vintilă, & Gherghina, 2018), while liquidity reflects a firm's capacity to meet short-term obligations, potentially mitigating price fluctuations (Gylych, Jibrin, Celik, & Isik, 2020; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). Yet, despite these established theoretical links, empirical evidence on the impact of firm-specific characteristics on share price volatility in Nigeria's industrial sector remains scarce and inconclusive.

Addressing this gap, the present study investigates how firm attributes such as leverage, profitability, liquidity, and firm age influence share price volatility among industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. By focusing on a sector central to Nigeria's industrial transformation, this study contributes to the broader discourse on firm-level determinants of market stability in emerging economies. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for investors, policymakers, and corporate managers seeking to enhance market efficiency, strengthen firm valuation mechanisms, and support evidence-based financial decision-making.

Based on the above, this study hypothesizes thus:

- i. financial leverage does not exert significant positive influence on share price volatility among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria*
- ii. profitability does not have significant positive relationship with share price volatility among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria*
- iii. liquidity does not have significant positive influence on share price volatility among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.*

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Firm-Specific Attributes

Firm-specific attributes, often described as internal or microeconomic variables, are unique characteristics inherent to individual firms that significantly influence their financial performance, risk profile, and market valuation. These attributes provide critical insights into a firm's operational efficiency, financial health, and strategic management practices (Oyedokun, Umoh, Haruna, & Zakari, 2019; Helmi & Ahmed, 2024; Chidi, 2024). By reflecting the internal dynamics of a business, firm-specific attributes not only affect a company's intrinsic value but also shape investor perceptions and risk assessments, thereby

impacting share price volatility. In the context of the Nigerian stock market, particularly within non-financial sectors, analyzing these internal factors offers a clearer understanding of how firm-level dynamics drive market behaviour in emerging economies (Nieuwoudt & Hall, 2022).

2.1.2 Financial Leverage

Financial leverage refers to the extent to which a firm relies on debt financing to support its operations and asset base, commonly assessed through indicators such as the debt-to-equity or debt-to-assets ratio. While leverage can enhance returns on equity through the tax advantages of debt and the magnification of earnings in favorable market conditions, it simultaneously increases a firm's fixed financial commitments. These obligations persist irrespective of revenue performance, thereby heightening exposure to financial distress and amplifying overall risk. Higher levels of leverage may possibly erode investor confidence and contribute to greater fluctuations in share prices (Akhtar et al., 2023). Furthermore, highly leveraged firms tend to exhibit heightened sensitivity to macroeconomic shocks, as economic downturns or interest rate increase can exacerbate debt-servicing burdens and intensify stock price volatility (Arhinful & Radmehr, 2023).

2.1.3 Profitability

Profitability represents a fundamental indicator of a firm's financial performance and managerial efficiency. It reflects the firm's ability to generate income from its resources while effectively controlling operational costs and optimizing asset utilization. Common measures such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Net Profit Margin capture different dimensions of this performance. ROA measures how effectively assets are employed to generate earnings, ROE assesses the return generated for shareholders' investment, and profit margin reflects the firm's efficiency in converting revenues into net income (Supriyadi, 2021).

From a theoretical standpoint, profitability serves as a key signal in capital markets. According to the signaling theory, higher profitability conveys positive information about a firm's future cash flows and managerial competence, thereby enhancing investor confidence and reducing perceived risk. Profitable firms are often viewed as financially sound, operationally efficient, and capable of sustaining long-term growth. Consequently, investors demand lower risk premiums for holding their shares, which can stabilize market valuations and dampen share price volatility (Supriono, 2022).

Expectedly, firms exhibiting superior profitability ought to experience less volatile stock price movements since they may have stronger earnings base; thus, making them resilient against market fluctuations. No doubt, profitability not only reflects internal performance efficiency but also plays a critical role in shaping investor perceptions and moderating stock price volatility in capital markets.

2.1.4 Liquidity

Liquidity reflects a firm's ability to meet its short-term financial obligations as they fall due, without resorting to external financing or asset liquidation under distress. It is commonly evaluated using indicators such as the current ratio and quick ratio, which measure the adequacy of current assets in covering current liabilities. A firm with strong liquidity

demonstrates prudent working capital management and financial flexibility, enabling it to navigate short-term shocks and maintain operational continuity (Gunawan, 2023).

From an investment perspective, liquidity serves as an important proxy for financial stability and risk exposure. Firms with ample liquid resources are better positioned to withstand periods of revenue decline, unexpected expenses, or credit tightening, thereby reducing the likelihood of financial distress. High liquidity also instils investor confidence, as it signals effective financial management and the ability to meet obligations promptly. This perception of lower risk often translates into reduced required rates of return and, consequently, diminished share price fluctuations.

From an empirical standpoint, Moridu and Abidin (2023) find that firms with stronger liquidity profiles tend to exhibit lower stock price volatility, primarily due to their enhanced operational resilience during economic downturns or market stress. Conversely, firms with weak liquidity may face heightened uncertainty, as investors anticipate potential financing constraints or default risk, leading to greater price sensitivity to adverse news. Hence, liquidity not only functions as a measure of short-term solvency but also plays a stabilizing role in capital market valuation dynamics.

2.1.5 Share Price Volatility

Share price volatility refers to the degree of variation or fluctuation in a company's stock price over a specific period of time. Alajekwu and Ezeabasili (2020) note that stock price volatility represents the degree of price fluctuations due to market information, complicating future price predictions. It measures the extent to which a stock's price moves upward or downward around its average or mean value. In essence, it captures the uncertainty or risk associated with changes in a firm's market valuation.

Share price volatility is influenced by a combination of internal firm-specific factors and external macroeconomic or institutional variables. In markets like Nigeria, structural inefficiencies exacerbate volatility, making the study of firm-specific determinants essential for understanding market dynamics. Challenges such as limited information disclosure, low investor education, thin trading, weak corporate governance enforcement, and political instability contribute to heightened volatility in the Nigerian capital market (Kemei, 2021; Buluma, 2021).

According to Dhingra et al. (2024), understanding volatility is critical for investment strategy formulation and market stability, particularly for non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group. Given the unique economic and institutional context of emerging markets, firm-specific attributes including leverage, profitability, liquidity, industry type, and market capitalization play pivotal roles in shaping share price behaviour.

2.2 Conceptual Model

Figure 2.1: Firm-Specific Attributes and Share Price Volatility Model
 Source: Researchers' Model (2025)

2.3 Theoretical Framework

2.3.1 Signaling Theory

The Signaling theory, was first proposed by Spence (1973); though in the context of labour markets; where he explained how one party (the “signaler”) conveys credible information to another party (the “receiver”) in situations of information asymmetry. In corporate finance and accounting contexts, the theory posits that managers possess superior information about a firm’s true performance, prospects, and risk profile compared to external investors. To reduce this asymmetry and influence market perception, managers engage in signaling activities. Such signaling activities includes actions or disclosures that credibly convey firm quality to investors and other stakeholders.

Within the framework of the signaling theory, indicators like profitability, dividend payments, leverage, profitability, liquidity, industry classification, market capitalization capital structure decisions, and voluntary disclosures are often interpreted as signals of firm strength and managerial confidence. For instance, high profitability or regular dividend payments may signal operational efficiency and stable future cash flows, while conservative leverage ratios can signal prudent risk management.

In capital markets, positive signals typically enhance investor confidence, reduce perceived risk, and stabilize share prices, whereas negative or ambiguous signals can trigger uncertainty and increase volatility. Consequently, signaling theory provides a relevant foundation for examining how firm specific attributes inform investor behaviour and stock price dynamics in the Nigerian context.

2.4 Empirical Review

A significant body of research has examined the interplay between firm-specific attributes and stock price volatility across various sectors and countries. In Nigeria, numerous studies have focused on manufacturing and non-financial firms with mixed but insightful findings. Olaoye et al. (2016) investigated the effect of profitability proxies (earnings yield, dividend yield, dividends per share, and return on total assets) on stock price volatility among five manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). They found that earnings yield, dividend yield, and dividends per share significantly influence volatility, while return on total assets had no significant influence on stock price volatility; thus, highlighting the importance of profitability metrics, especially dividend-related measures, in explaining stock price behaviour within the manufacturing sector.

Similarly, Abba and Usman (2016) examined the effect of corporate attributes like firm size, leverage, profitability, liquidity, and growth on share prices of pharmaceutical firms. The outcome of the study indicated that firm size, leverage, profitability, and growth exerted positive and significant influence on share price; whereas, liquidity was negatively related to share price. Furthermore, Bashir (2018) examined data from 32 manufacturing firms and found that firm size, firm age, and market concentration had positive relationship with share prices, whereas internal governance mechanism negatively influenced share prices. In another study, Daud (2018) however established dividend yield and payout ratios play some stabilizing roles in mitigating stock price volatility among Nigerian conglomerates, while growth opportunities and earnings volatility exacerbated such stabilizing roles.

Within Nigeria's consumer goods and banking sectors, Anachedo et al. (2021) reported that earnings per share and sales growth exhibited negative and insignificant relationship with stock prices, while operating cash flows exerted significant positive influence on share price. Ezeagu et al. (2022) and Olaoye and Ekundayo (2022) confirmed the value relevance of dividend per share, earnings per share, and book value per share in Nigerian deposit money banks, highlighting their positive influence on share prices. Tonye and Ogbise (2022) found limited significant effects of profits and sales growth on stock prices in Nigerian pharmaceutical firms, while studies like Lyndon and Ebipudo (2019), Uniamikogbo et al. (2019), and Ememobong et al. (2023) further reflect mixed; yet, critical influences of accounting information, dividend policies, and firm attributes on stock price volatility and earnings predictability.

Beyond Nigeria, similar patterns have been reported by prior studies as Memon et al. (2021) found a significant negative relationship between financial leverage and share price for Pakistani automobile firms, with firm size positively influencing valuation. Also, the study of Nuridah et al. (2022) reported that sales growth positively affects stock prices in Indonesian manufacturing consumer goods firms, though return on equity had no significant partial effect. Arhinful and Radmehr (2023) analyzed Tokyo Stock Exchange data and reported that while leverage ratios negatively impact performance metrics like ROE and EPS, certain solvency measures have positive effects on them.

More recent studies like those of Salman et al. (2024) reported that dividend per share and solvency margin ratio exhibited positive relationship with market prices of insurance firms, whereas, the reverse is the case for book value per share and earnings per share respectively. Wafula and Miroga (2024) reinforced the importance of dividend payout and yield in

explaining share price volatility for Kenyan construction firms. Ndubuisi et al. (2025) highlighted that profitability and firm size are key positive drivers of share prices in Nigerian financial and non-financial firms.

3.0 Methodology

This study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design, which is appropriate when analyzing historical data without manipulating variables. The population for this research consists of thirteen industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 31, 2023. Out of these, ten firms were purposively sampled based on specific selection criteria to ensure relevance and data adequacy. This approach facilitates focused analysis while maintaining representativeness within the industrial goods sector on the NGX.

Table 3.1: Sample Selection Criteria

Sector/criteria	Number of firms
No of firms	13
Less: Industrial goods (non-available Data)	01
Less: Industrial goods (Incomplete Data)	02
Total sample size	10

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

Data were extracted from the annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms, covering the period from 2014 to 2024. The key variables include leverage, profitability, liquidity, firm age, and percentage change in share price. To analyze the relationships among these variables, the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) regression technique was adopted. GMM is particularly well-suited for this study due to its robustness in handling dynamic panel data models with lagged dependent variables, endogeneity concerns caused by omitted variables, measurement errors, and simultaneity. Unlike ordinary least squares (OLS), GMM corrects for heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation, providing consistent and efficient parameter estimates, especially important given evidence of non-normality in the data.

Based on the theoretical literature and earlier empirical studies, the present study adapted the model of Ologunwab et'al (2022) to express the econometric form of the model presented as:

$$SPV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FLEV_{it} + \beta_2 PROF_{it} + \beta_3 LIQ_{it} + \beta_4 FAGE_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

The Apriori expectation based on the literature reviewed and related theories is stated as follows; $\beta_1 X_{1it} > 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} < 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} < 0$. The basis for this expectation flows from the outcome of the literature review and empirical findings.

Where:

β_0	=	Constant
$\beta_1 - \beta_3$	=	Slope Coefficient
μ	=	Stochastic disturbance
i	=	i^{th} company
t	=	period

3.2 Description of variables

Table 3.2: Description of variables

Label	Variable type	Description	Measurement	Source
SPV	Dependent	Share Price Volatility	Measured by Percentage Change in Share price	Miharsi, Gamayuni, and Dharma
FLEV	Independent	Leverage	Measured by the ratio of Total Debt to total asset	Odoemelam et'al (2019)
PROF	Independent	Profitability	Measured by the ratio of Net Income to Total Asset	Marshall Hargrave (2025)
LIQ	Independent	Liquidity	Current asset/Current Liabilities	Brigham and Houston (2015)

Source: Author's Compilation (2025)

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The section dealt extensively with the regression results alongside each of their policy implications. Also, some preliminary analyses were conducted before running the main regression analyses that was used to test the hypotheses.

4.1 Preliminary Tests

The following preliminary tests were considered before the main regression was presented:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	SPV	FLEV	PROF	LIQ	FAGE
Mean	0.140374	0.445793	0.088514	2.070504	26.56000
Median	0.011295	0.420213	0.085631	1.625869	29.00000
Maximum	3.934783	1.399168	0.539594	11.24961	49.00000
Minimum	-0.714450	0.032253	-0.139664	0.252386	1.000000
Std. Dev.	0.564307	0.206367	0.109636	1.799738	13.15895
Skewness	3.989789	0.678120	1.395534	2.676763	-0.261402
Kurtosis	23.99447	6.581275	6.975442	11.08747	1.863106
Jarque-Bera	2101.840	61.10382	98.30913	391.9475	6.524379
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.038304
Sum	14.03744	44.57927	8.851404	207.0504	2656.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	31.52581	4.216133	1.189993	320.6666	17142.64
Observations	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Share Price Volatility (SPV): The mean value of 0.1404 indicates the average level of stock price fluctuations over the sample period. The median value of 0.0113 suggests that most observations are clustered around lower volatility levels, but the maximum value of 3.9348 points to some instances of very high volatility. The high standard deviation of 0.5643 indicates considerable variability in share price fluctuations among the firms. The skewness value of 3.9898 reveals a right-skewed distribution, meaning there are some firms with exceptionally

high volatility. The kurtosis of approximately 24 further suggests a leptokurtic distribution, with a high tendency for extreme values. The Jarque-Bera test statistic (2101.84) and a probability value of 0.00 confirm that the data significantly deviate from normality, indicating the presence of non-normal distribution in the data for share price volatility.

Furthermore, the summary statistics for financial leverage (FLEV) indicate that the average leverage ratio stood at 0.4458, while the median value was 0.4202, indicating that most firms have moderate leverage levels. The maximum leverage of approximately 1.3991 means that some firms are highly leveraged, while the minimum of 0.0323 is an indication that some firms have very low level of leverage. The standard deviation of 0.2064 reflects moderate dispersion; whereas, the skewness of 0.6781 and the kurtosis value of about 6.58 is an indication that a relatively symmetric distribution with some degree of peakedness exist; though the Jarque-Bera statistic of 61.10 and a p-value of 0.00 aptly confirms that the data for leverage across the entire panel are not normally distributed.

The result for profitability (PROF) indicate that the average profitability measure is 0.0885, with a median close at 0.0856, and a maximum of 0.5396. The standard deviation of 0.1096 indicates some variation in profitability ratios across firms. Skewness of 1.3955 suggests right-skewed data, and kurtosis of 6.98 signals a distribution with some outliers. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 98.31 and a p-value of 0.00 indicate significant non-normality.

In terms of liquidity (LIQ), the mean liquidity ratio obtained is 2.0705, with a median of 1.63, a maximum of 11.2496, and a minimum of 0.2524. The high standard deviation of 1.7997 points to substantial variability in liquidity levels among firms. The skewness of 2.6768 indicates right-skewness, and kurtosis of 11.09 confirms a leptokurtic distribution with potential outliers. The Jarque-Bera value of 392 and a p-value of 0.00 strongly indicate non-normality.

Firm Age (FAGE) recorded an average value of 26.56 years, with a median of 29 years, and a maximum age of 49 years; thus, indicating a relatively mature sample of firms. The standard deviation of 13.16 years is a testament that a moderate dispersion exists relative to the age of the sampled firms. The negative skewness (-0.2614) and kurtosis of 1.86 suggest a nearly symmetric distribution with fewer outliers. The Jarque-Bera test yields a value of about 6.52 with a p-value of 0.038, indicating slight deviations from normality but less severe than other variables.

Overall, the descriptive statistics reveal diverse variability, non-normal distributions, and skewness across the variables, justifying the use of robust estimation techniques such as GMM in subsequent analysis to cater for the existing heteroskedasticity and distributional issues.

Table 4.2: Normality Test

Parameter	Jarque-Bera	Probability	Observations	Decision
SPV	2101.840	0.000000	100	Reject normality
FLEV	61.10382	0.000000	100	Reject normality
PROF	98.30913	0.000000	100	Reject normality
LIQ	391.9475	0.000000	100	Reject normality
FAGE	6.524379	0.038304	100	Reject normality

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.2 presents the results of the Jarque-Bera normality test for the variables in the study. The Jarque-Bera test assesses whether the data follows a normal distribution by comparing the sample's skewness and kurtosis to those expected under normality. For all variables Share Price Volatility (SPV), Financial Leverage (FLEV), Profitability (PROF), Liquidity (LIQ), and Firm Age (FAGE) the test statistics yield very low p-values (all below the conventional 0.05 significance level). This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that the data are normally distributed. In practical terms, it means that the data for all variables significantly deviate from normality. This justifies the use of robust econometric methods like the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), which do not assume normal distribution and can provide consistent and efficient estimates even with such data properties.

4.1.3 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis is used to test the degree and direction of linearity between the dependent and independent variables. The result is therefore presented in table 4.2:

Table 4.3: Spearman Correlation

	SPV	FLEV	PROF	LIQ	FAGE
SPV	1.000000				
FLEV	-0.033435	1.000000			
PROF	0.052313	0.174377	1.000000		
LIQ	0.002532	-0.587615	-0.268616	1.000000	
FAGE	0.077076	0.180519	-0.130142	-0.218240	1.000000

Source: Fieldwork, 2025 (Using Eview)

The correlation analysis uses Spearman's rank correlation to measure the strength and direction of the monotonic relationship between share price volatility (SPV) and firm-specific variables (leverage, profitability, liquidity, and firm age). The resulting coefficients show that SPV has very weak correlations with leverage (-0.033), profitability (0.052), liquidity (0.003), and firm age (0.077), indicating little to no monotonic association in the sample data. Notably, leverage and liquidity are strongly negatively correlated (-0.588), suggesting that companies with higher debt levels tend to have lower liquidity. Profitability also negatively correlates with liquidity (-0.269), while firm age shows moderate positive correlations with leverage (0.181) and weak negative correlations with profitability and liquidity. These coefficients suggest mostly weak and mixed relationships, justifying further analysis with more robust econometric methods to capture complex dynamics beyond simple bivariate associations.

Table 4.4: Multicollinearity Tests Outcome

Variables	FLEV	PROF	LIQ
VIF	1.528	1.0782	1.5968
Tolerance Value	0.6544	0.9274	0.6264

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The multicollinearity test results in Table 4.4 show the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance values for the independent variables: Financial Leverage (FLEV), Profitability (PROF), and Liquidity (LIQ). The VIF values range from approximately 1.08 to 1.60, which are well below the commonly accepted threshold, indicating that multicollinearity is not a concern among these variables (see Jeroh, 2016; Jeroh, 2020a; Jeroh, 2020b; Jeroh, 2020c;

Jeroh, 2020d Ukolobi & Jeroh, 2020). Correspondingly, the tolerance values, which are the reciprocal of VIF, are all above 0.25, further confirming low multicollinearity. This means that the predictors are not highly correlated with each other, so their estimated regression coefficients will be reliable and the regression model is stable. Overall, these results suggest that multicollinearity will not distort the analysis or inference in this study.

4.2. Regression Analysis

Given the significant departures from normality in the residuals and share price volatility data, the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) technique is employed as a statistically robust alternative. GMM enhances the reliability of parameter estimates by effectively addressing issues such as heteroskedasticity, endogeneity, and dynamic relationships through the use of instrumental variables and robust weighting matrices. This approach ensures consistent, unbiased, and valid inference even when classical assumptions like normality and homoscedasticity are violated, thereby strengthening the credibility of the study's regression results.

Table 4.5

Dependent Variable: SPV

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Date: 07/24/25 Time: 20:40

Sample: 1 100

Included observations: 100

Linear estimation with 1 weight update

Estimation weighting matrix: HAC (Bartlett kernel, Newey-West fixed bandwidth = 5.0000)

Standard errors & covariance computed using estimation weighting matrix

Instrument specification: FLEV ROA LIQ

Constant added to instrument list

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FLEV	-0.170778	0.314079	-0.543741	0.5879
PROF	0.449844	0.608158	0.739682	0.4613
LIQ	0.006460	0.021931	0.294545	0.7690
FAGE	0.006149	0.004844	1.269337	0.2074
R-squared	0.012148	Mean dependent var		0.140374
Adjusted R-squared	-0.018722	S.D. dependent var		0.564307
S.E. of regression	0.569565	Sum squared resid		31.14282
Durbin-Watson stat	1.908914	J-statistic		5.25E-46
Instrument rank	4			

Source: Fieldwork, 2025 (Using Eview)

The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimation presented analyzes the relationship between share price volatility (SPV) and the independent variables: financial leverage (FLEV), profitability (PROF), liquidity (LIQ), and control variable firm age (FAGE) using 100 observations. The model employs a heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC)

weighting matrix with Newey-West adjustments to produce robust standard errors. The coefficient for FLEV is negative (-0.171) but statistically insignificant ($p = 0.588$), indicating no meaningful effect on SPV. PROF's coefficient is positive (0.450) yet also insignificant ($p = 0.461$), suggesting a weak positive relationship with volatility. LIQ shows a near-zero positive coefficient (0.006) with high insignificance ($p = 0.769$), and FAGE reveals a minor positive but non-significant effect (0.006, $p = 0.207$). The low R-squared value (0.012) indicates the explanatory variables account for little variation in SPV. The Durbin-Watson statistic of approximately 1.91 suggests no strong autocorrelation issue. The J-statistic value, close to zero, supports instrument validity. Overall, the GMM results suggest that leverage, profitability, liquidity, and firm age do not have statistically significant impacts on share price volatility in this sample, emphasizing the possibility of complex or omitted factors influencing volatility beyond these firm-specific attributes.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the effect of financial leverage (FLEV), profitability (PROF), and liquidity (LIQ), with firm age included as a control variable on share price volatility (SPV), among listed firms using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) across 100 observations. Key findings are as follows:

- i) Financial leverage (FLEV) had a negative, but not statistically significant effect on SPV ($\beta = -0.170778$, $p = 0.5879$), indicating that higher leverage is associated with reduced share price volatility.
- ii) Profitability (PROF) exhibited a positive and statistically insignificant effect on SPV ($\beta = 0.0449844$, $p = 0.4613$), implying that more profitable firms experience moderate volatility in their share prices.
- iii) Liquidity (LIQ) had a negative but statistically insignificant effect on SPV ($\beta = 0.006460$, $p = 0.7690$), suggesting that liquidity does not influence share price volatility in this sample.

Although profitability and firm age show positive relationships with volatility, these are not significant in explaining fluctuations. Leverage exhibits a negative but insignificant effect, and liquidity's influence is marginal. The low explanatory power of the model suggests that share price volatility is influenced by other factors beyond these firm-specific attributes. Additionally, the diagnostic tests confirmed the presence of non-normality and heteroskedasticity, justifying the use of the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) method, which provided consistent and robust parameter estimates.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. While firm-specific attributes studied here showed limited influence on share price volatility, managers should maintain prudent financial policies, specifically by optimizing leverage to balance risk and return. Strengthening profitability and liquidity

remains critical to boosting firm stability and investor confidence, which can indirectly help stabilize share prices.

- ii. Based on the finding that financial leverage (FLEV) had a negative but statistically insignificant effect on share price volatility (SPV), we therefore recommend that managers should not rely solely on leverage to control stock price fluctuations but instead adopt a balanced approach that integrates other financial and operational strategies to stabilize their firm's market valuation.
- iii. Since profitability does not significantly influence volatility, firms should focus on other strategies beyond profit generation to stabilize their share prices. Managers could consider implementing robust risk management practices, maintaining prudent financial policies, and ensuring transparent communication with investors.
- iv. Liquidity showed a negative but statistically insignificant effect on share price volatility in this study's sample, suggesting no clear direct impact. Nonetheless, maintaining adequate firm liquidity remains important, as broader research indicates that higher liquidity generally supports market stability and reduces volatility. Therefore, it is recommended that firms prioritize sound liquidity management to ensure operational resilience and investor confidence, while market regulators and policymakers should foster conditions that enhance overall market liquidity to promote efficient and stable trading environments.

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